

Diffusion trends of rice varieties in Matara district, southern Sri Lanka, 1988-92 DS and WS.

*Many farmers abandoned ricefields due to unusually excessive amounts of water at plant establishment.

appropriate to the local production conditions, although its farmgate price is low. Similarly, At85-1 is gaining popularity, especially in the upper areas of the district where soil acidification is high. ■

Rice - fish - azolla farming system for low-lying ricefields

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Fish culture in ricefields is a good way for farmers to gain additional protein and income. We studied the economics of the rice - fish - azolla system during 1992 in a low-lying ricefield at ARS.

The soil was sandy loam with pH 7.2, EC 0.1 dS/m, 229 kg available N/ha, 14 kg available P/ha, and 151 kg available K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with

three replications. Calotropis (12.5 t/ha) was incorporated as green leaf manure 10 d before transplanting rice variety ADT 36, which was fertilized with 120-38-38 kg NPK/ha. *Azolla microphylla* was applied at 2.0 t/ha as fish feed/N fixer, 5 d after transplanting (DT). Different systems were studied (see table).

Field trenches (1 m deep × 1 m wide) were dug for fish shelter. These trenches occupied 10% of the riceland. *Catla*, *rohu*, and *mrigal* were stocked 10 DT at an equal ratio of 3,000 fingerlings/ha. A mixture of banana pseudostem and cow dung (1:1) and rice bran were fed as supplementary feed at the rate of 5% of

average fish body weight.

Rice - azolla produced the most grain, which was at par with rice - fish - azolla - calotropis system (see table). Rice - fish - azolla - calotropis system was more profitable than rice alone, recording an additional income of US\$40.70/ha and the highest benefit-cost ratio (1.30) of the systems studied. Rice yield was slightly less under rice -fish system because of the trenches; the fish harvest, however more than compensated for the reduced rice yield.

This study indicates that rice - fish - azolla farming is possible in low-lying ricefields of Tamil Nadu. ■

Yield, yield attributes, and economics of different rice, azolla, and fish systems. ARS, Bhavanisagar, Tamil Nadu, India, 1992.

System	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Fish yield (kg/ha)	Net income (US\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice	417	20.9	101	88	19.7	5.0	-	81.95	1.21
Rice - fish	431	21.1	102	92	19.4	4.8	71	84.95	1.21
Rice - azolla	475	21.1	108	94	19.7	5.3	-	103.90	1.27
Rice - azolla - fish	482	21.7	114	98	19.4	5.0	75	104.70	1.26
Rice - azolla - calotropis - fish	502	21.7	114	99	20.1	5.2	78	122.65	1.30
Rice - azolla (no N)	284	18.1	95	81	18.8	3.9	-	36.35	1.17
Rice - azolla - calotropis (no N)	364	19.7	95	85	19.0	4.2	-	50.65	1.15
LSD (0.05)	69.4	ns	8.6	8.9	ns	.3	-	-	-